

Synthesis in the Iminazole series : Some derivatives of Isiminazole.

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The iminazole group contains many substances which are formed in the metabolic processes of the living organism. Among these oxo-derivatives like hydantoin, allantoin and parabanic acid are of special importance. While the 2-4-di-oxo-derivatives are largely represented only a few 4-5-di-oxo-derivatives are known. The synthesis of parabanic acid from urea and oxalyl chloride (Biltz and Topp, *Ber.*, 1913, 46, 1387), and of *o*-methyl *iso*-parabanic acid from *o*-methyl *iso*-urea and oxalic ester (Bruce, *Amer. Chem. J.* 1904, 26, 456) led us to investigate the action of oxalyl chloride, oxalic ester and oxaminic ester on amidines. With benzamidine and *p*-toluamidine dioxo-dihydro-iminazoles are easily obtained. With acetamidine however, our labours have, so far, not been attended with success, due probably to the great instability of acetamidine (Pinner: "Die Imidoether," p. 107).

From the dioxo-compounds the oxo-chloro derivatives may be easily obtained by the action of phosphorus oxychloride.

It is interesting to note that the oxo-chloro-compounds may be regarded as representatives of the hitherto unknown group of *isiminazoles*.

EXPERIMENTAL.

2-Phenyl-4:5-dioxo-4:5-dihydro-iminazole.

(1) From oxalic ester and benzamidine.

Potassium hydroxide (1.12g.) dissolved in water (5 c. c.) was added to benzamidine hydrochloride (3 g.) dissolved in water (10 c. c.) in a stoppered bottle. Then oxalic ester (3 c. c.) was quickly added. Heat was generated and an intense yellow colour developed. The bottle was cooled and the yellow colour gradually faded. The mixture was allowed to stand for three or four days with occasional shaking. The solid product was collected, washed with water and recrystallised from alcohol.

It is soluble in water, alcohol and glacial acetic acid, insoluble in ether and acetone; m. p. 174° with decomposition. (Found: N=15.82. $\text{C}_9\text{H}_6\text{O}_2\text{N}_2$ requires N=16.09 per cent.).

(2) From oxalyl chloride and benzamidine.

Benzamidine was liberated from the hydrochloride by means of concentrated potassium hydroxide solution. The free base was extracted by ether and a little more than the calculated quantity of oxalyl chloride was added drop by drop, with constant stirring. After about an hour the ether was evaporated by keeping it in a vacuum desiccator and the residue crystallised from alcohol. It was identical with the substance already obtained, (Found: N=15.77).

2-Phenyl-4-chloro-5-oxo-isiminazole.

Freshly distilled phosphorus oxychloride (5 c. c.) was added to the dioxo compound (5 g.) in a flask fitted with

a condenser. The mixture was heated on the water-bath for fifteen minutes and then poured on a small quantity of crushed ice. The solution was nearly neutralised with sodium carbonate, evaporated to dryness and extracted with absolute alcohol. On concentrating the solution, the chloro compound separated in shining needles, m.p. 215° with decomposition. It is very soluble in water and alcohol, insoluble in ether and benzene. (Found: Cl = 18.41. $C_9H_5ON_2Cl$ requires Cl = 18.44 per cent.).

2-p-Tolyl-4-5-dioxo-dihydro-iminazole.

(1) From oxalic ester and *p*-toluamidine.

p-Toluamidine hydrochloride (3.4 g.) potassium hydroxide (1.12 g.) and oxalic ester (3 c.c.) were treated in the same manner as in the case of benzamidine. After standing overnight the solid product was crystallised from a large quantity of boiling water. It does not melt up to 280° .

It is soluble in hot water, warm alcohol, acetic acid and hydrochloric acid, insoluble in acetone and benzene. (Found: N = 14.68. $C_{10}H_8O_2N_2$ requires N = 14.88 per cent.).

(2) From oxalyl chloride and *p*-toluamidine.

The procedure was the same as in the case of benzamidine. (Found: N = 14.71 per cent.).

(3) From oxaminic ester and *p*-toluamidine.

Oxaminic ester (2.1 g.) was added to a dry ethereal solution of *p*-toluamidine liberated from the hydrochloride (5 g.) and the mixture was well-shaken. The odour of ammonia was distinctly perceptible. The mixture was allowed to stand for a day and the solid product was recrystallised from alcohol. The substance was found to be identical with the product obtained with oxalic ester or oxalyl chloride. (Found: N = 14.73 per cent.).

2-p-Tolyl-4-chloro-5-oxo-isiminazole.

The dioxo compound (5 g.) was heated with phosphorus oxychloride (5 c.c.) on the water-bath for about fifteen minutes and then poured over a small quantity of crushed ice. The hydrochloride separated in the form of crystals. It was filtered and dissolved in a small quantity of water and poured into a concentrated solution of sodium acetate. The crystalline precipitate was filtered and dried and crystallised from a mixture of alcohol and ether. The substance sublimes between 260 and 265°.

It is very soluble in water, soluble in alcohol, insoluble in chloroform, acetone and ether. (Found : Cl = 17.2. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_7\text{ON}_2\text{Cl}$ requires Cl = 17.19 per cent.).

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